

Development Program, introduced the 2526 strain from Malaysia in 1973. Because the line was heterogeneous, it was further selected at Suakoko for adaptability and uniformity. The released population of Suakoko 8 is fairly uniform, photoperiod insensitive, and matures in about 140 days. It has good seedling vigor; good tillering ability; semicompact plant type; intermediate culms of intermediate diameter;

intermediate senescence; well-exserted, long, and heavy panicles; glabrous, pale green, and intermediate leaves; and erect flag leaves. Its grains are long, slender, and translucent. It suffers less damage than IR5 from the important diseases such as blast, sheath rot, sheath blight, leaf scald, and brown spot, as well as caseworm. Because it is photoperiod insensitive, Suakoko 8 is also superior to Gissi 27. Its plant type is well suited to

Liberian peasant farm conditions of imperfect water control, moderate fertilization, and manual harvesting.

During the 1977 wet season, Suakoko 8 seed were distributed for minikit and production kit trials. Seed is expected to reach a large number of farmers for planting in the 1978 wet season. **W**

India's national gene bank in international cooperation

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The national rice germ plasm bank of India is maintained at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. The collection started with about 2,000 varieties obtained from the paddy breeding station, Coimbatore, in 1946–47. It gradually increased as varieties were obtained from different

states and abroad by request and exchange. About 10,000 additional varieties were added from systematic surveys from Jeypore tract of Orissa (1955–59); Manipur state (1965–70); northeastern India (Assam Rice Collection, 1968–71); and new collections, mostly from upland and rainfed tracts of nine states (1976–77). The national gene bank at present consists of 14,905 varieties (Table 1).

Supplying traditional cultivars to scientists and institutions inside India and abroad is an important activity of

the national center. About 5,000 varieties have been sent to scientists and institutions in 24 countries during the last decade. A few countries and institutions that have received large numbers of accessions, particularly from 1974 to 1977, are shown in Table 2. **W**

Newest rice varieties in 10 Asian nations

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

To determine the types of new rice varieties going out to farmers in Asia, IRRI surveyed rice breeders at 29 research centers in 10 countries on the varieties that had been released by their stations during the previous 5 years. The research project, initiated in 1975, was partially funded by a research grant from the Rockefeller Foundation.

Twenty-seven of the experiment stations had released 165 new varieties (two stations had not released any varieties during the time period). For all stations surveyed, the average number of released varieties was 5.7, or a little more than one new variety per year. For only the stations that had released varieties during the 5-year period, the average was 6.1 varieties/station.

Next, each breeder was asked how many of the new varieties had been bred locally (within his country) and how many had come from IRRI. Breeders were also asked to name the parents of locally bred varieties.

Seventy-eight percent of the 165 varieties had been bred in the countries where they were released; 22% were developed at IRRI (see figure).

Table 1. Present status of national gene bank at Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Source	Varieties (no.)			Total
	Early maturity	Medium maturity	Late maturity	
World collection (AC no.)	1,386	1,254	924	3,564
Jeypore Botanical Survey (JBS no.)	241	1,006	321	1,568
Manipur collection (MNP no.)	40	495	224	759
Assam Rice Collection (ARC no.)	447	4,874	207	5,528
Miscellaneous collection	550	1,155	350	2,055
New collection from states (NCS no., duration not yet classified)	—	—	—	1,431
Total	2,664	8,784	2,026	14,905

Table 2. Countries and institutions that have received major supplies of seed from the national gene bank, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Country	Varieties supplied (no.)				Total
	1974	1975	1976	1977	
IRRI (Philippines)	22	24	65	2,893	3,004
USSR	22	32	41	253 ^a	348
West Africa	28	34	69	8	139
Vietnam	—	41	9	—	50
USA	—	—	1	33	34
Liberia	—	35	—	—	35
Total	72	166	185	3,187	3,610

^a Includes material committed to be sent.

Of 165 new rice varieties released to farmers in Asia over a 5-year period, 64% either were progeny of IRRI rices or were IRRI varieties or experimental lines. Twenty-two percent of the rices were developed at IRRI and 42% were progeny of local crosses involving an IRRI parent. One hundred and sixty-five newest varieties released from 1970 to 1975 at 29 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Forty-two percent of the varieties were progeny of crosses involving an IRRI variety or line as a parent. (Of the 129 locally developed varieties, 54% were IRRI progeny.) A total of 64% of the sample of 165 newest varieties in 10 countries were either progeny of IRRI rices or had been developed at IRRI. ❧

Advanced breeding lines in 10 Asian nations

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

Because most of the future rice varieties released for farmer use in Asia will come from advanced yield trials, IRRI collected information on the types of plant materials included in the trials. Rice breeders were surveyed at 28 research centers in 10 countries in mid-1975. The research project was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation.

It was found that 4,163 advanced breeding lines were being tested in 29 yield trials at the 28 stations. The mean number was 144 lines/trial, with a range of from 12 to 630 lines/trial.

For most of the trials, the responsible breeder indicated how many of the advanced lines were developed at that

Data were collected on 4,021 breeding lines of rice in 27 advanced yield trials in Asia. *a*. Fifty-nine percent of the advanced lines originated from crosses made at the local research centers; 41% originated from crosses made outside of the local centers. *b*. Of 1,406 introduced lines in 17 trials, 60% came from other research centers in the same country and 39%, from IRRI. From a survey of advanced experimental lines of rice in 9 Asian nations, 1975.

station and how many came from outside sources (other breeding centers in that country, other countries, or IRRI). These data were collected on 4,021 breeding lines in 27 advanced yield trials in 9 countries.

Fifty-nine percent of the genetic material (2363 lines) originated from local crosses made at the breeders' stations; 41% (1658 lines) originated outside of the stations (see figure, *a*).

Next, the origin was determined of the introduced lines (the advanced lines that did not come from local crosses). Data were obtained for 1,406 of the introduced breeding lines in 17 advanced yield trials in 8 countries.

Sixty percent of the introduced genetic material (842 lines) came from crosses made at other research centers within the same country as the surveyed experiment station; 39% (543 lines) came from IRRI; and about 1% (21 lines) came from breeding programs in other Asian nations (see figure, *b*).

To further measure the diversity of the genetic background of improved local lines, breeders at 20 research centers in 8 countries were asked to indicate the number of crosses from which they selected 3,791 locally developed lines in 22 advanced trials. The lines had been selected from 443 crosses – an average of 8.6 advanced lines/cross. ❧

Effect of seedling on the growth and yield of rice varieties

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Rice varieties Bala, Saket 1, and Ratna were transplanted at 24, 29, 34, 44, and 49 days to study the growth behavior and extent of yield reduction when transplanting is delayed. The experiment was conducted at Allahabad Agricultural

Institute during the 1976 kharif season using a split-plot design with four replications. Varieties were in main plots and seedlings of different ages were in subplots.

When older seedlings of the short-duration variety Bala were transplanted, tiller number and yield were consistently reduced. Saket 1 and Ratna (medium- and long-duration rices) gave higher values when planted at 29 days of age than when planted at any other age (see table). The short-duration variety may be transplanted until the age of 34 days,